

**A SURVEY ON THE PREFERRED STRAND OF PUBLIC
SECONDARY HIGH SCHOOL STUDENTS OF
ALABEL MUNICIPALITY**

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A Survey on the Preferred Strand of Public Secondary High School Students of Alabel Municipality

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Abstract

This study accentuated on the determinants of senior high school tracks and strands inclination of Grade 10 students of the five (5) secondary schools in Municipality of Alabel: Alabel National High School, Alabel Integrated SPED Center, Alegria National High School, Kawas National High School, and Tokawal National High School. It used a quantitative descriptive-survey method of research that involved 788 respondents utilizing a descriptive survey method of research to gather the data needed. Frequencies and percentages were utilized to verify the respondents' tracks and strands preferences. Based on the findings of the study, the majority of the preferred senior high school tracks and strands of the Grade 10 students were not included in the offerings of the five secondary schools in the Municipality of Alabel. With these results an Intervention Program Matrix was made in order to help the schools to open senior high school tracks and strands based on the needs of the communities. Through this, students will be able to be ready to enroll in college programs that are aligned with their senior high school tracks and strands. Based on the findings of the study, it is highly recommended that every school must have intensive career advocacy on the parents and students for proper guidance.

Keywords: *guidance and counseling, senior high school tracks and strands, public secondary students, intervention program matrix*

Introduction

Every Filipino believes that education is an essential tool for success. It encourages everyone to step forward and excel in creating positive effects where recognition and achievement can be attained. It has provided everyone with the ability to think critically in ways to make better decisions in life, to be able to cope and handle different life challenges, and to generate motivation for everyone in order to have better prospects needed to grow in their own chosen career path in life.

Around the world, education has received focus attention among everything else because it determines the future of every individual in the country. Among the nations worldwide, Philippines was the last country in Asia and one of the only three countries in the world with a 10-year education program before entering college. To align the country's curriculum and meet the needs of the global market, where quality education is a must for everyone, the Philippine educational system adapted to a modern and more dynamic curriculum and followed a 12-year program (Abueva, 2019).

Moreover, this is rooted and strengthened by the legal base of the Republic Act 10533 or also known as the "Enhanced Basic Education Act of 2013". In this act, the State shall establish, maintain, and support a complete, adequate, and integrated education system relevant to the needs of every Filipino people, the country, and society at large. Likewise, it is hereby declared in the policy of the State that every Filipino graduate of a primary education program shall be an empowered and holistic individual who has learned, through a program that is rooted on sound educational principles and engaged towards excellence, the foundations for learning throughout life, the competence and excellent to engage in work and be productive, the ability to coexist in fruitful harmony with local and global communities, the capability to engage in autonomous, creative, and critical thinking, and the capacity and willingness to transform others and one's self (Republic Act 10533).

Section 3 of this Act states that the Basic Education System is intended to meet all the basic learning needs, providing the foundation for future learning. It embraces kindergarten, elementary, and secondary education levels and alternative learning systems for out-of-school learners and those with learners with special needs.

Moreover, Section 4 states that the Enhanced Basic Education Program encompasses at least one (1) year of kindergarten education, six (6) years of elementary education, and six (6) years of secondary education in that sequence. Secondary education includes four (4) years of junior high school and two (2) years of senior high school education.

The implementation of the K–12 program in the Philippines aimed at producing more skilled students with essential skills for lifelong learning and employment. This program has promoted the mutual recognition of Filipino learners and professionals in other countries because they were able to master the skills and learn the core competencies that were essential to meeting the demands of the global market. This new program has prepared learners for jobs, entrepreneurship, and middle-level skills development since they had to graduate at 18 (Abueva, 2019).

Making a career decision is one of life's most challenging and complex processes, especially for students. They need to know that their college choices are vital to their future. Altering one's study path may sometimes result in a poor job choice, wasting money and time,

and aggravating one's workplace.

The significant change in the K–12 curriculum was the additional two years in secondary education, also known as senior high school (SHS). The old 4-year secondary curriculum was called Junior High School (JHS), which starts from Grade 7 to Grade 10, and Senior High School follows through from Grades 11 to 12. The additional two years of SHS mean that the high school graduates are more equipped for whatever paths they choose and have reached legal age (18 years old) to be lawfully employed after graduation (Dangoy & Madrigal, 2020).

The career specializations offered by the K–12 curriculum served as a stepping stone for the learners to plan and act upon their chosen careers. In the Division of Sarangani, the schools' tracks offered were identified by the Department of Education Division Office. Alabel is the capital town of Sarangani province; as a developing municipality and the center of excellence, the secondary schools must also offer all tracks in senior high school to cater to all students and give them all the choices they may want to pursue in higher education (Dangoy & Madrigal, 2020).

In connection with this, the five center schools in the Municipality of Alabel, namely Alabel National High School only offers a Technical Vocational Track with six specializations; Alegria National High School offers ABM with 107 students; Kawas National High School provides ABM with 12 students and Aquaculture Strand under the TechVoc Track with 44 students; Tokawal NHS offers ABM with 36 students and Agriculture Strand under the TechVoc Track with 33 students; and the Alabel Central Sped Integrated School offers HUMSS with 35 students and ABM with 14 students.

Furthermore, not all tracks are offered in every school; for this reason, many students had transferred out last year to other private schools that offered the tracks and strands they wanted that would fit their interests and skills. A recorded total of ninety-six (96) students from Alabel NHS transferred to other schools, particularly in General Santos City; Sixteen (16) students from Alegria NHS; fifteen (15) from Kawas NHS; twelve (12) from Tokawal NHS; and fourteen (14) students from Alabel Sped Integrated School. Thus, it was essential to determine the different senior high school tracks and strand choices of the Grade 10 students in these five secondary schools as a basis for a track expansion plan in the Municipality of Alabel for the next school year.

Research Objectives

This study aimed to investigate the senior high school tracks and strands choices of Grade 10 students for the school year 2016-2017 in the five center schools in the Municipality of Alabel: Alabel National High School, Alabel Integrated SPED Center, Alegria National High School, Kawas National High School, and Tokawal National High School as the basis for a track expansion plan for the school year 2017-2018. Specifically, it endeavored to answer the following questions:

1. To determine the senior high school track and strand choices of Grade 10 students in the five center schools in the Municipality of Alabel.
2. To propose an intervention program based on the findings of the study.

Methodology

This section contains the research design and methodology used to conduct this study. It incorporated the sampling technique, sources of data, the research subjects, the study population, the instrument used to gather data, and the statistical tools employed in processing the data. This chapter shows how the researcher obtained the necessary data for the study and how these data were analyzed, interpreted, and presented as easily as possible.

Research Design

This study utilized the descriptive survey method to determine the Senior High School Track choices of Grade 10 students of Alabel National High School, Alabel Sped Integrated Center, Alegria National High School, Kawas National High School, and Tokawal National High School for the Academic Year 2016-2017. It also used quantitative methods to assess the respondents' feedback.

A descriptive survey research design is a systematic and structured approach to collecting data from a sample of individuals or entities within a larger population, with the primary aim of providing a detailed and accurate description of the characteristics, behaviors, opinions, or attitudes within the target group. This method involves using surveys, questionnaires, interviews, or observations to collect data, which is then analyzed and summarized to conclude the population of interest. It is an influential tool scientists and researchers use to gather information about a particular group or phenomenon. This type of research provides a detailed and accurate picture of the characteristics and behaviors of a particular population or subject. By observing and collecting data on a given topic, descriptive research helps researchers gain a deeper understanding of a specific issue and provides valuable insights that can inform future studies (Shrutika, 2023). The research survey tool included all the different senior high school tracks and strands that Dep Ed offers, so that the learners-respondents may choose according to what aligns with their interest and skills. The result can be used as the basis for a track expansion plan in the Municipality of Alabel and certain institutions planning to design and implement the Senior High School Program.

Participants

The research respondents in this study were the SY 2016-2017 Grade 10 from Alabel National High School, Tokawal National High School, Alegria National High School, Kawas National High School, and Alabel Central Integrated Sped Center. The Grade 10 students were chosen as respondents since they were the second batch of the Senior High School in the K-12 Program. The hundred percent (100%) population per school was used as the research respondents.

Table 1. *Distribution of Respondents*

<i>Schools</i>	<i>Population</i>		<i>Total</i>
	<i>Male</i>	<i>Female</i>	
Alabel NHS	146	237	383
Alabel SPED	49	65	114
Alegria NHS	45	55	100
Kawas NHS	39	48	87
Tokawal NHS	63	41	104
Total	342	447	788

Instruments

This study used a survey rating scale/questionnaire to gather the respondents' feedback. The survey questionnaire comprised all the different tracks and strands of the Senior High School. The respondents' feedback was tallied as the basis for the proposal of a track expansion plan in the Municipality of Alabel.

This research survey form was adapted from the Republic of the Philippines Department of Education Guidelines on the Implementation of Senior High School (SHS) Program in existing Public Junior High Schools (JHSs) and Integrated Schools (ISs), Establishment of Stand Alone Public SHSs, and Conversion of Existing Public Elementary and JHSs Into Stand-Alone SHSs.

Data Collection

Upon approval of the study's title and attesting the instruments valid and reliable, the researcher sought permission from the school's division superintendent of Dep Ed Sarangani to distribute the questionnaires and conduct the study.

After the superintendent's approval, a letter requesting permission was sent to the five school heads where the study was conducted: Alabel National High School, Alabel Integrated Sped Center, Alegria National High School, Kawas National High School, and Tokawal National High School.

The researcher then distributed the survey forms and conducted the study personally at the school heads' approved time.

A hundred percent of Grade 10 learners were the study's respondents. Before conducting the study, the researcher met with the class advisers. The study was conducted to inform the students about the survey and to avoid absences to ensure the learners' hundred percent attendance. The study was conducted per classroom to avoid disruption of classes and to cater to the learners' questions and clarifications.

Before the survey forms were distributed, the students received a short classroom orientation. During orientation, the students discussed the purpose of the study, the description of every senior high school track and strand to ensure that their choices aligned with their interests and skills, and the impact of their choice on the schools where they are enrolled.

Statistical Tools

After the researcher had collected the data from the respondents through the instrument, they were gathered and tallied to be scored. The researcher constructed a tabulation diagram for the gathered data. In the process, the researcher tallied the answers, organized them, and prepared for the statistical treatment with appropriate tools based on the questions raised in Chapter 1. These were analyzed, and the data was gathered.

The respondents' feedback was treated using frequency counts and percentages to get the total responses in every track and strand.

Ethical Considerations

A primary critical consideration had distinct implications for this quantitative research. These issues and concerns came out basically from the methodology involved in this study. The ethical concerns applicable to this research were the study's appropriate operation, confidentiality, and anonymity. This study followed the standards of the Ramon Magsaysay Memorial Colleges Ethics and Review Committee for the guidelines of ethical consideration, particularly in addressing the population and data such as, but not limited to:

Voluntary Participation. The participants were given the choice to participate without any expectation of consequences or loss of advantages. As a result, after the participants were informed of the study's goals and advantages, it became clear that their rights to contribute to the body of knowledge were carefully considered and anticipated. In this study, the participants were not forced to

participate. They were permitted to withdraw their involvement if they felt uncomfortable during the study.

Privacy and Confidentiality. In compliance with the Data Privacy Act of 2012, which safeguards the fundamental human right to privacy, participants have the right to privacy, which may not be infringed upon without their informed consent.. Moreover, concern over privacy and participant protections for humans was one barrier to data exchange. By protocol, the researcher was concerned with preserving the privacy and safety of research participants.

Informed Consent Process. The prospective research participants were to be fully informed about the research's objectives, methods, and benefits as comprehensively as possible within the framework of the study. The consent of the participants was obtained, indicating that their participation was asked for voluntarily.

Recruitment. The participants were informed why they had become part of the study. To help the participants understand what the study was all about, I explained the purpose of the study so that they could infer from the researcher and view the essence of the study. Apart from the letter, I discussed the rationale of the study and its significance.

Benefits. This study was valuable to the participants since the results may act as an eye-opener for the DepEd authorities, school administrators, and all teachers to grasp the value of senior high school track and strand offerings. Furthermore, to achieve more benefits in research, the researcher did all the aspects that would not harm the participants' lives and, thus, would benefit from further undertakings about the related studies. The rise of meaningful learning was the most essential part of achieving benefits.

Plagiarism. The study ensured no trace or evidence of misinterpretation of someone else's work. It was to be subjected to plagiarism detectors like Grammarly or Turnitin software. As a researcher, I felt a need to have positive character and integrity, which were associated with moral virtues and values. The researcher needed better knowledge about the paradigm of plagiarism to have a credible research paper.

Fabrication. The study had no indication or cue of purposive misinterpretation of what had been done. There must have been no making up of data and results or purposely putting forward conclusions that were not accurate. The researcher employed and integrated theories related to the information and other inferential concepts.

Results

This section presents, analyzes, and interprets the data gathered. It deals with the presentation, analysis, and interpretation of data, which is done according to the sub-problems asked in Chapter 1.

Table 2. Senior High School Track and Strand Choices of Grade 10 Students in Alabel National High School

SHS	Strands	Specialization	Male	Female	Total	Percent
Tracks						
Academic	Accountancy, Business and Management (ABM)		20	30	50	13%
	Humanities and Social Sciences (HUMMS)		43	62	105	27%
	Science, Technology and Engineering and Mathematics (STEM)		28	38	66	17%
	Home Economics (HE)	Food and Beverages Service NCII	7	16	23	6%
Technical-Vocational Livelihood	Information and Communication Technology (ICT)	Hairdressing NCII	6	27	33	9%
		Tailoring NCII	2	10	12	3%
		Computer Hardware Servicing NCII	11	26	37	10%
	Agri-Fisheries Agriculture	Aquaculture	0	0	0	0%
		Agriculture	0	0	0	0%
Sports Arts and Design	Industrial Arts	Electrical Installation and Maintenance NCII	13	16	29	8%
		Shielded Metal Arc Welding (SMAW) NCII	16	12	28	7%
			0	0	0	0%
Total			146	237	383	100%

Table 2 presents the Senior High School Track and Strand choices of Grade 10 students in Alabel National High School. It implied

that most Grade 10 students in Alabel NHS preferred the Academic Track and the strands under this, particularly the HUMSS strand with 105 students or 27%, followed by STEM with 66 students with 17% and ABM with 50 students at 13%.

Table 3. Senior High School Track and Strand Choices of Grade 10 Students in Alabel Integrated SPED Center

SHS	Strands	Specialization	Male	Female	Total	Percent
Tracks						
Academic	Accountancy, Business and Management (ABM)		3	8	11	10%
	Humanities and Social Sciences (HUMMS)		12	18	30	26%
	Science, Technology and Engineering and Mathematics (STEM)		10	13	23	20%
	Home Economics (HE)	Food and Beverages Service NCII	1	3	4	4%
		Hairdressing NCII	0	2	2	2%
		Tailoring NCII	0	1	1	1%
Technical-Vocational Livelihood	Information and Communication Technology (ICT)	Computer Hardware Servicing NCII	5	11	16	14%
		Agri-Fisheries Agriculture	1	0	1	1%
			0	0	0	0%
	Industrial Arts	Electrical Installation and Maintenance NCII	9	3	12	10%
Shielded Metal Arc Welding (SMAW) NCII		8	6	14	12%	
Sports Arts and Design			0	0	0	0%
Total			49	65	114	100%

Table 3 presents the Senior High School Track and Strand choices of Grade 10 students in Alabel Integrated SPED Center. The data shows that the academic track is the most preferred for Grade 10 students. HUMSS got the highest score of 30 students with 26%; then STEM got 23 students with 20%, Computer Hardware Servicing NCII under TVL Track got 16 students who preferred this with 14%, followed by Shielded Metal Arc NC II under TVL with 14 students and 14%, Electrical Installation and Maintenance with 12 students and 10%, Accountancy Business and Management (ABM) under Academic Track were the choices of 11 students at 10%, Food, and Beverage followed it with only four students and equivalent to 4%.

Table 4. Senior High School Track and Strand Choices of Grade 10 Students in Alegria National High School

SHS	Strands	Specialization	Male	Female	Total	Percent
Tracks						
Academic	Accountancy, Business and Management (ABM)		4	5	9	9%
	Humanities and Social Sciences (HUMMS)		8	8	16	16%
	Science, Technology and Engineering and Mathematics (STEM)		9	14	23	23%
	Home Economics (HE)	Food and Beverages Service NCII	2	3	5	5%
		Hairdressing NCII	1	2	3	3%
		Tailoring NCII	1	2	3	3%
Technical-Vocational Livelihood	Information and Communication Technology (ICT)	Computer Hardware Servicing NCII	4	7	11	11%
		Agri-Fisheries Agriculture	1	0	1	1%
			0	0	0	0%
	Industrial Arts	Electrical Installation and Maintenance NCII	8	6	14	14%
Shielded Metal Arc		7	7	14	14%	

Welding (SMAW) NCII					
Sports Arts and Design		0	0	0	0%
Total		45	55	100	100%

Table 4 presents the Senior High School Track and Strand choices of Grade 10 students in Alegria NHS. 23 Grade 10 students chose STEM Strand under Academic Track, 16 students chose HUMSS Strand under Academic Track, there are 14 students with 14% who preferred Shielded Metal Arc Welding (SMAW) under TVL Track, and 14 students wor 14% chose Electrical Installation and Maintenance NC II under TVL track, 11 out of 100 or equivalent to 11% students preferred the Computer Hardware Servicing NCII under TVL track. There were nine students, or 9% choosing ABM under the Academic Track, and the Aquaculture under the TVL track got the lowest score of 1 student only or 1%.

Table 5. Senior High School Track and Strand Choices of Grade 10 Students in Kawas National High School

SHS	Strands	Specialization	Male	Female	Total	Percent
Tracks						
Academic	Accountancy, Business and Management (ABM)		5	8	13	15%
	Humanities and Social Sciences (HUMMS)		4	20	24	28%
	Science, Technology and Engineering and Mathematics (STEM)		4	6	10	11%
	Home Economics (HE)	Food and Beverages Service NCII	0	3	3	4%
		Hairdressing NCII	0	2	2	2%
		Tailoring NCII	0	1	1	1%
Technical-Vocational Livelihood	Information and Communication Technology (ICT)	Computer Hardware Servicing NCII	3	5	8	9%
	Agri-Fisheries Agriculture	Aquaculture	9	3	12	14%
			0	0	0	0%
	Industrial Arts	Electrical Installation and Maintenance NCII	10	0	10	11%
		Shielded Metal Arc Welding (SMAW) NCII	4	0	24	5%
Sports Arts and Design			0	0	0	0%
Total			39	48	87	100%

Table 5 presents the Senior High School Tracks and Strands choices of Grade 10 students in Kawas NHS. There were 24 Grade 10 students or 28% preferring to choose HUMSS Strand under Academic Track, 13 students or 15% chose ABM Strand under Academic Track, 12 students with 14% preferred Aquaculture under TVL Track, a total of 10 students or equivalent to 11% preferred to enroll in STEM under Academic Track, another ten students with also 11% preferred Electrical Installation and Maintenance NCII under TVL Track, eight students or equivalent to 9% wanted to enroll in Computer Hardware and Servicing NC II under TVL Track, while only one student or equivalent to 1% preferred to enroll in Tailoring NC II under TVL Track.

Table 6. Senior High School Track and Strand Choices of Grade 10 Students in Tokawal National High School

SHS	Strands	Specialization	Male	Female	Total	Percent
Tracks						
Academic	Accountancy, Business and Management (ABM)		6	11	17	16%
	Humanities and Social Sciences (HUMMS)		18	18	30	29%
	Science, Technology and Engineering and Mathematics (STEM)		9	6	18	14%
Technical-Vocational	Home Economics (HE)	Food and Beverages Service NCII	2	2	4	3%

Livelihood	Hairdressing NCII	3	2	8	8%
	Tailoring NCII	1	0	1	1%
Information and Communication Technology (ICT)	Computer Hardware Servicing NCII	8	2	10	10%
	Agri-Fisheries Agriculture	0	0	0	0%
Industrial Arts	Aquaculture	8	2	10	10%
	Electrical Installation and Maintenance NCII	9	0	9	9%
	Shielded Metal Arc Welding (SMAW) NCII	0	0	0	0%
Sports Arts and Design		0	0	0	0%
Total		63	41	104	100%

Table 6 presents the Senior High School Track and Strand choices of Grade 10 students in Tokawal NHS. There were 30 Grade 10 students, with 29% preferring the HUMSS Strand under Academic Track, 17 with 16% choosing ABM Strand under Academic Track, and 15 with 14% preferred STEM Strand under Academic Track.

Further analysis of the results revealed that the track and strand with most of the Grade 10 students in the municipality of Alabel chose were not present in their respective schools.

Technical-vocational schools are very important; in this offering, students who do not have the necessary skills will quickly struggle in their new position. They may start to lose confidence and feel unsure about what to do. The businesses that hire them will also feel frustrated as they lose money and time. They find themselves training new employees who do not have the insight and practical knowledge they need to do what they were hired to do."Vocational education and training allow students to gain practical experience in their chosen career path before graduation."

Students who finish those rigorous programs have the credentials and training they need to start immediately in their chosen career path. Not only do the students feel confident in their abilities, but the employers themselves know that they have made a solid choice in their new hire and can count on them to begin excelling in the position quickly (Peters, 2021).

The survey results indicated that most of the tracks and strands that the Grade 10 students preferred to enroll for Senior High School in the Municipality of Alabel, particularly in Alabel NHS, Alabel SPED, Alegria NHS, Kawas NHS, and Tokawal NHS, were not included in the list of choices in their respective schools. Therefore, these schools should expand the number of tracks and strands offered for SHS students.

It means that that they choose to prepare as their career is what they want to live in the future. This implies that the track and strand they prefer may lead them to the career they want, and these can lead them to the employment of their interests in the future.

Jaapar et al. (2018) emphasized along the idea of these results that the students whose course work organized around a career goal would be more satisfied with their education than those students whose coursework was not related to career goals of interest had higher educational aspirations.

As Forster et al, have cited, and emphasized that students need to know what course or career they are learning that would fit them in their world (Forster & Bol, 2018). Moreover, vocational high school graduates are expected to enter the field of work readily. Nevertheless, the number of vocational high school graduates who were unemployed is still high. Optimizing a career guidance service requires complete evaluation feedback. In detail, this research aimed to identify a constructed instrument applicable to evaluating a career guidance program at a vocational high school; develop an evaluation model; and examine the measurement, structure, and effectiveness of the model.

The research's approach and development employed Borg & Gall's model. The test for the product was addressed to nine vocational high schools in Yogyakarta. The validity and reliability instruments were verified through expert judgment, alpha Cronbach analysis, Exploratory Factor Analysis (EFA), testing the measurement model, and the structural model was verified using partial least square (PLS) SmartPLS 3.0. The product constituted a career guidance evaluation model at a vocational high school, complete with its application, manipulation, and analysis up to recommendation construction.

Moreover, the EFA test results showed six measurement factors of counseling service: assertiveness, career readiness, self-awareness, career awareness, work characteristics, and positive attitude towards guidance and counseling service. The quality instrument product of TADIPHE consists of the target component (3 items), assessment (13 items), design (13 items), installation (22 items), process (44 items), the result (70 items), and effectiveness of the program (7 items). The result of the partial least square shows that all predictors contribute (Q2) as much as 88.91% and 11.09%; the rest may be determined by other variables (Martaningsih & Istiyono, 2019).

Moreover, the present research investigated the role of career salience (or the perceived importance of work and a career) in

occupational choice and satisfaction. It was predicted that career salience would positively relate to the degree of self-occupational congruence in an occupational choice. The correlation between congruence and occupational satisfaction would be greater for high career-salient subjects than for low career-salient subjects. Males supported the first hypothesis, and the second hypothesis received no support. The relationships between career salience and other vocationally related variables were reported and related to prior research (Kreisman & Stange, 2020).

Discussion

This section summarizes findings, conclusions, and recommendations for the study investigated.

This study aimed to survey the Senior High School Strand of Grade 10 students in the Municipality of Alabel and to propose an expansion of tracks and strands in the municipality. It was conducted among five secondary schools: Alabel National High School, Alabel Integrated SPED Center, Alegria National High School, Kawas National High School, and Tokawal National High School.

It was quantitative research using survey rating scale questionnaires, involving 788 Grade 10 students for the School Year 2016-2017. Frequency count and percentage tests were employed to treat the data gathered.

Based on the data gathered, the following were the findings made:

There were 383 Grade 10 respondent students in Alabel National High School. After surveying them, it was revealed that 105 students preferred to enroll in HUMSS, 66 students preferred to enroll in STEM, 30 students preferred to enroll in ABM, 4 students preferred to enroll in TVL-Hairdressing NC II, 26 students preferred to enroll in TVL-Computer Hardware NC II, 16 students preferred to enroll in TVL-Food and Beverages NC II, 16 students preferred to enroll in TVL- Electrical Installation and Maintenance NC II, 12 students preferred to enrolled in TVL-Shielded Metal Arc Welding (SMAW) NC II. In comparison, there were only eight students who preferred to enroll for the TVL-Tailoring NC II.

The research study on a proposed career recommendation system showed that it aimed to help not only the guidance counselor but especially the senior high school students themselves by guiding them in considering numerous factors associated with their decision on what career they would pursue.

Moreover, in choosing the student attributes from numerous factors, a feature selection technique is appropriate to remove irrelevant features that affect the performance of the proposed fuzzy-based system. This paper uses different filter methods to select the best attributes, which are used as crisp inputs. The result of the experiment shows reasonable results for making decisions. It is concluded that the proposed career-recommended system for the students is very timely and will be one of the significant research works in the new era of education in the Philippines (Natividad, 2019).

Self-esteem is a person's overall self-worth or personal value; it is how people appreciate and love themselves, often seen as a personality trait. This also means being stable and enduring; people who have low self-esteem cannot take up a world filled with optimism and determination or have difficulties in interacting with other people to help develop themselves by determining the benefits of choosing the Humanities and Social Sciences (HUMSS) Strand to develop the self-esteem of the students through different activities that HUMSS offers. The researchers used the descriptive method to describe the characteristics of the population or phenomenon being studied to provide information by using a survey questionnaire so that the respondents could easily express their thoughts and ideas about a certain topic or study (Natividad, 2019).

Furthermore, choosing the right career for a person could give him satisfaction. This is supported by a study conducted by Quines and Pinero, which aimed to determine the mediating effect of job satisfaction on the relationship between teamwork skills and the work values of teachers. Utilizing quantitative, non-experimental design via correlational technique, data were obtained from 300 elementary public school teachers who belong to the three districts, Magsaysay, Bansalan, and Matan-ao, under the Division of Davao Del Sur, in the province of Davao Del Sur. The researcher utilized a stratified random sampling technique and an online survey mode of data collection. The researcher also utilized statistical tools such as mean, Pearson *r*, and path analysis. From the results of the study, it was found that there is a high level of mean scores for all variables of teamwork skills, work values, and job satisfaction of teachers (Quines & Piñero, 2022).

Hence, extracurricular activities comprised 3.95% of the total, which helped the students develop their confidence by joining any sport or club at school. Interpersonal skills were 3.66%, where the students could confidently express appropriate emotions to others. Developing student self-esteem will help them gain more knowledge, improve their research skills, and teach them how to communicate without uncertainty. The study found that academic performance, extracurricular activities, and interpersonal skills significantly affected the development of students' self-esteem.

Thus, the whole-day class schedule has gained general recognition for being effective in enhancing students' learning. It may also have longer school hours and additional resources provided by the education to enhance the quality of education of every student. In a whole-day class schedule, the students can enjoy more diverse learning experiences. Normally, students spend an average of 12 hours a day in school. In addition, these may include programs or activities for promoting knowledge to students (Magana et al., 2020).

The survey results in Alabel National SPED Center showed that out of 114 Grade 10 students, 30 chose HUMSS, 23 chose STEM, 16 chose TVL—Computer Hardware Servicing NC II, 14 chose TVL-Shielded Metal Arc Welding (SMAW) NC II, 12 chose Electrical Installation and Maintenance NC II, 11 chose ABM, 4 chose TVL-Food and Beverages Service NC II, 2 chose TVL-Hairdressing NC II, 1 chose TVL-Tailoring NC II, and 1 chose TVL-Aquaculture.

The result of this survey was also highlighted on the research study, which examined the perception of Humanities and Social Science teachers among public Senior High Schools in the Department of Education's Humanities and Social Sciences strand in the Philippines. It uses Erden's element-based evaluation model by considering the alignment to the goals of the Humanities and Social Sciences disciplines, the purpose, core courses of the program, and the teaching-learning process.

It also used Tyler's Rationale as a framework for assessing the curriculum. Likewise, the study examined the problems and difficulties in curricular implementation. Upon administering a survey to 25 Humanities and Social Science teachers among four public senior high schools, data revealed that the respondents perceived the curriculum goals and the program's purpose as highly observed. In contrast, the core courses of the program and teaching-learning process were satisfactorily observed in the curriculum. Also, sex and age were not factors in their level of assessment of Humanities and Social Science goals. The problems and difficulties encountered by teachers included unbalanced time allocation of learning competencies, lack of available learning materials, and lack of specialized teachers.

Based on the findings, it is suggested that the government provide stronger teacher support programs to address the gap in curriculum implementation. The K to 12 program also needs a full review, as the study only provides a pre-survey of more significant institutional issues. While the Humanities and Social Science curriculum appears aligned with the goals of their disciplines and the country's educational goals, its realization still depends upon the teachers' implementation at the classroom level (Estrera, 2020).

A study by Ramos (2021) that involved Senior High School students under the TVL program in Batangas, Philippines, emphasized the importance of the TVL track and strand. They put technical vocational education in the limelight. The offering of techno education in various schools aims to equip the students with the skills and knowledge needed to choose middle-level employment after graduation. This study aims to serve as a guide to school administrators to effectively implement the program despite the challenges (Ramos, 2021).

Many influences affect the preferences of grade 10 students in choosing a track to proceed to senior high school. Likewise, this study aimed to identify the influence of preference of a Senior High School track that Grade 10 students commonly encountered in terms of gender, socioeconomic status, average academic grades, nature of parent's occupation, strand, and the level of influence of the respondent to be associated with preferences in choosing a track in senior high school in terms of family influence-decision; peer influence; financial condition; and employability. The research tool was a survey questionnaire.

The questionnaire was composed of the respondent's profile and 10 statements to be rated. The factors that fairly influenced the preferences of senior high school students. In terms of gender, male students considered their socioeconomic status and their parents' occupation as factors in choosing their track in Senior High School, while female students considered their peers as a factor in choosing a track in Senior High School (Nazareno et al., 2021).

Another respondent school where the survey was conducted at Kawas NHS. Here the result showed that out of 87 Grade 10 students, 34 preferred to enroll in HUMSS, 13 preferred to enroll in ABM, 12 preferred to enroll in TVL-Aquaculture, 10 preferred in TVL-Electrical Installation and Maintenance NC II, 10 preferred STEM, eight preferred TVL-Computer Hardware Servicing NC II, four preferred TVL-Shielded Metal Arc Welding (SMAW) NC II, 3 preferred Food and Beverages Service NC II, two preferred TVL-Hairdressing NC II, and only one preferred Tailoring NC II.

The result above aligns with the study conducted by Naelga, Sofia C.; Blane, Aelyn R. of the Department of Education, Division of Misamis Oriental, they made efforts in preparation for the full implementation of the Senior High School in 2016. Several conferences, seminars, and meetings have been conducted with TESDA and CHED, to name a few. Critical to the success of the Grade 11 to 12 implementation is identifying the technical-vocational (tech-voc) track from among the four tracks that can be offered for Senior High School. This study aimed to determine the tech-voc strands from which the top three specializations were identified (Naelga & Blane, 2017).

The teacher-respondents were from the District of Claveria-2, Claveria, Misamis Oriental. The district has three secondary schools: Dr. Gerardo Sabal Memorial National High School, Hinaplanan National High School, and Patrocinio National High School. An interview was also conducted in the Public Employment Service Office (PESO) to identify the types of industries that could be partners of senior high school during student-work immersion. A descriptive research method was employed to achieve the objectives of the study in which the survey questionnaires identified the strengths of the district, in general, and the schools in particular, to offer the identified specializations based on faculty qualification, school capacity like buildable space, existing laboratories, equipment, and tools; and potential industry linkages (Naelga & Blane, 2017).

Another study was conducted in Punta Integrated School to focus on the main objective of the K to 12 Basic Education Curriculum implementation, which is to develop learners' competencies, skills, and values relevant to pursuing further education and/ or joining the world of work. To achieve greater congruence between basic education and the nation's development targets. Under the K to 12

Voucher Program, Junior High School completers can enroll in either public or private schools of their choice; for any reason, this indicates that many of them would prefer to enroll outside public schooling. The Punta Integrated School is one of the 11 pioneers of Senior High School implementers in the Division of Calamba City.

Currently, the school offers an academic track with two strands (GAS and ABM) and two strands in Technical-vocation (ICT and bread and pastry). For two consecutive years since the implementation of the Senior High School, there has been an average of 33.61% enrolment in the year 2015-2016 and 38.77% last S. Y 2016-2017.

This means that more than half of the population of Junior High School completers are enrolled outside their home school (Garcia, 2019).

The result in Tokawal NHS showed that out of 104 Grade 10 students, 30 students preferred to enroll in HUMSS, 17 preferred to enroll in ABM, 15 preferred to enroll in STEM, ten preferred to enroll in TVL-Agriculture, nine preferred to enroll in TVL-Shielded Metal Arc Welding (SMAW) NC II, eight preferred to enroll in TVL-Computer Hardware Servicing NC II, five preferred to enroll in TVL-Hairdressing NC II, five preferred to enroll in TVL-electrical Installation and Maintenance NC II, four preferred to enroll TVL-Food and Beverages, and only one preferred to enroll in TVL-Tailoring NC II.

Moreover, qualitative descriptive research explored the perspectives of STEM (science, technology, engineering, and mathematics) senior high school students in a public secondary school in Zambales, Philippines, on their reasons for enrolling in STEM and their intent to pursue a relevant career. A total of 20 Grade 12 students were purposively selected as research participants. The participants were interviewed using a validated structured interview guide. The recorded interviews were individually transcribed to arrive at an extended text. The extended texts were reviewed to generate themes and significant statements.

The paper found that senior high school students are generally interested in the field related to biology. The alignment to the preferred course in college is the primary reason for the participants enrolling in STEM. Almost all the students wanted to pursue STEM-related careers after their university graduation. Further, personal aspiration is the main reason for the participants to pursue STEM-related professions. The study recommends that senior high schools may design various activities during career week. These activities may include possible career paths in STEM-related courses, students' career and motivation, and their career aptitude. Teachers may also infuse innovative pedagogies for better STEM instruction. For the students to have more interest in science, it is recommended that STEM teachers undergo retooling or pursue advanced studies. Senior high schools may conduct career guidance seminars for the students on what strands they should take.

The Department of Education (DepEd) may support implementing different programs regarding students' career preparation. This program will help the students become more aware of what career path they want to pursue and avoid pressure from peers. Schools may advocate a collaborative, authentic, and goal-oriented learning environment concerning the demands of Industrial Revolution 4.0 (Rafanan & De Guzman, 2020). The K-12 Program was implemented in the Philippines for six years, causing students to choose various senior high school tracks for their education after junior high school. Students are about to choose one career track, but some may struggle to select a career path due to several factors. Hence, the National Career Assessment Examination (NCAE) administration provides students with options in choosing the appropriate career path.

The main purpose of this study was to determine the students' scholastic aptitude, occupational preference, and academic track inclinations as the basis for a proposed career pathing program for their current grade level. The researchers utilized a quantitative descriptive design, applying frequency and percentage distribution and ranking as statistical treatments to identify the scholastic aptitude, occupational preference, and academic track inclination of the grade 9 students of the school year 2017–2018.

A convenience sampling method was used to select the Grade 9 students for the school year 2017-2018. Eighty-nine (89) students, composed of forty-six (46) male and forty-three (43) female students, were able to take part in the study. The scholastic aptitude, occupational preference, and academic track inclination were identified through the National and Career Assessment Examination (NCAE). The results showed that most of the students from the STEM strand fall under the excellent level. Moreover, students from the ABM and HUMSS strands fall under the above-average and average levels.

Lastly, most students from the GAS strand fall under the above-average level. Regarding the ranking of highly preferred occupations, science was ranked highest in the STEM and GAS strands. Business and finance/commerce was ranked highest in the ABM strand, and arts was ranked highest in the HUMSS strand. Moreover, male and female respondents' academic track inclination falls above average. The study found that most grade 9 male students' scholastic aptitude is above average. In contrast, most of the scholastic aptitude of grade 9 female students falls under the excellent level.

In addition, male respondents ranked science as the most preferred occupation, while arts was the highest-ranked among the female respondents. Regarding the academic track inclination of the respondents according to their track, the majority of STEM and HUMSS students fall under the above-average level, while the majority of ABM and GAS students fall under the average level. This study can be used by educators in providing career guidance and support to students needing career advice (Mallare et al., 2020).

Conclusion

Below is the conclusion formulated based on the data gathered. After a series of data gathering, tabulation, and interpretation, it was found and concluded that the majority of the preferred tracks and strands of the Grade 10 students in the Municipality of Alabel, particularly in Alabel NHS, Alabel Integrated Sped Center, Alegria NHS, Kawas NHS, and Tokawal, were not offered in their respective schools. Based on the results and conclusions made, the following may be recommended: (1) Further studies and research may be conducted on the impact of the career guidance program on Grade 10 students' decision-making process in choosing the tracks and strands they enrolled in senior high school. (2) Further research and studies may be conducted on factors affecting senior high school tracks and strand choices among Grade 10 students to understand more about students' choices. (3) Further research and studies may be needed to craft an intervention program to address the recommendation of choosing senior high school tracks and strands.

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